

LCA application on semi-extensive agro-silvo-pastoral systems

Introduction

In order to assess the environmental impact of semi-extensive beef cattle breeding, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analysis was carried out. Based on the results obtained from the LCA analysis and the evaluation of forest CO₂ absorption, it was possible to determine that the impact of semi-wild cattle breeding of the Maremma breed emits 8.05 kg of CO₂ eq per kg of live weight of cattle. In addition, it was estimated that the forest ecosystem was able to offset 66% of emissions in the form of climate-altering gases through the carbon stock in tree tissues. The exploitation of additional fodder resources (herbaceous and shrubby woodland) in addition to pasture and hay makes it possible to increase growth by reducing the animal farm residence. Furthermore, the diversification of fodder reduces the dependence on cereals with consequent economic and environmental benefits. The presence of trees reduces heat stress, makes it possible to maintain stable ingestion and growth levels even during the summer period, thus improves animal welfare.

Lessons learned

It's important to be careful with livestock load so as not to overload the system, but overall, silvopastoralism offers multiple benefits. The life cycle analysis showed that enteric methane emissions are partially mitigated by the carbon sequestration of the forests of the farmland.

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Further information

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